

Cellulose Fermenters from Horse-dung.

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The discovery of any suitable type or types of bacteria that would easily ferment cellulose is important for the practical utilisation of waste plant materials. Till lately, no bacteria were isolated which could carry on cellulose fermentation to such an extent and with such rapidity that the possibility of their industrial use could be thought of in the near future. The case of sewage bacteria which are made use of in isolated instances in the activated sludge processes is, however, different, as the nature of the liquor to be fermented there is complex and not typical of the kind of liquor usually available in cellulose fermentation. The economics of the activated sludge process have been questioned here and there, but the uniformity and the certainty which have been by now realised in sludge digestion, leave no doubt that as soon as a profitable use for methane is found, the process will have taken its place of importance. The bulkiness of the sludge digestion process and the comparatively long time required for the fermentation of resistant celluloses make the introduction of cellulosic matters from outside for the purpose of increased fermentation, impracticable. Hence, the treatment of cellulosic or lignocellulosic matters by chemical processes to convert them quickly into industrial products, with comparatively lesser outlay has had always a great attraction.

We had, therefore, undertaken laboratory investigation on the decomposition of cellulose by means of bacteria. Suitable types of bacteria cannot be said to have been isolated, although several mixed types carry on the degradation of cellulose under thermophilic conditions far enough to be technically promising. The products obtained by such bacterial fermentations are varied, but these could be grouped under two heads:—(i) Liquid products consisting of formic, acetic and butyric acids and alcohol and (ii) gaseous products consisting under usual circumstances, of methane, hydrogen and carbon dioxide, and under special circumstances, only carbon dioxide. The earliest researches on the fermentation of cellulose under anaerobic, mesophilic conditions were by Omeliansky (1895-1902), who isolated in more or less pure

condition, methane-fermenting and hydrogen-fermenting bacteria from the mud of the river Neva. But the credit of perceiving the importance of the action of thermophilic organisms on cellulose may be given to Macfadyen and Blaxall (*Trans. Inst. Preventive Medicine*, 1899, p. 162), who obtained enrichment cultures from stable manure capable of fermenting cellulose. Pringsheim (*Centr. Bakt. Abt.*, 1912, 38, 2) described a cellulose-destroying enzyme in a culture fermenting at 55°. He made further the very important observation that in the fermentation of cellulose, cellobiose and glucose are intermediate products. The qualitative nature of the products of cellulose fermentation is alike, as noticed by both sets of workers, acetic and formic acids being noticed by both of them. Thereafter, thermophilic cellulose fermenters were recognised to be fairly widely distributed in nature. Kroulik in 1913 described four species—3 plectridia and 1 with a central spore, 2 being aerobic, and 2 anaerobic. He was of the opinion that the two aerobic organisms which were abundant during the early stages of the fermentation were not cellulose fermenters, because when isolated on beef extract agar plates, they showed no activity. The anaerobic organisms did not grow on agar, thus showing an important distinction between the two. He found some of these cultures resistant to the action of steam and the production of acetic, butyric, formic and lactic acids was also noticed. The gases that evolved were found by him to be carbon dioxide and hydrogen. In any case, he failed to isolate pure cultures. Langwell and Lymn (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1923, 42, 280 r) published some interesting results on the fermentation of cellulose by thermophilic bacteria isolated from fermenting horse manure. It is claimed that large amounts of sulphite pulp were readily fermented with the production of acetic, butyric and lactic acids, ethyl alcohol, methane, hydrogen and carbon dioxide. These results have been doubted by some authorities and a detailed confirmatory report by the author would be extremely welcome on this very important work. Khouvine (*Ann. de l° Inst. Pasteur*, 1923, 37, 711) described an organism isolated from human faeces which was exclusively a cellulose fermenter, working at 35-51°, the main products of the fermentation were acetic acid, ethyl alcohol, carbon dioxide and small amounts of butyric acid and hydrogen. There was no distinct optimum temperature for the action of this organism and fermentation began only when some sterilised faecal extracts were added to the medium.

Neuberg and Cohn (*Biochem. Z.*, 1923, 139, 527) obtained from canal mud and horse manure enrichment cultures capable of fermenting cellulose at 53-55°. Viljoen, Fred and Peterson (*J. Agric. Science*, 1926, 16, 1) claim to have isolated a type of thermophilic cellulose fermenter in a pure condition from an infusion of 100 g. of a rapidly fermenting manure in 200 c.c. of water. Thaysen has doubted the purity of the bacterium isolated by the authors since they obtained the culture they describe as pure from a dilution containing as much as one ten-thousandth part of the crude culture, and from this dilution in cellulose agar they isolated not one well-circumscribed colony, but were content to employ as inoculant for their pure cultures a part of this agar medium containing a gas bubble. Even starting with a culture that is only slightly infected, it is highly improbable that the above procedure could lead to the isolation of pure cultures (*cf.* Thaysen and Bunker, "The Microbiology of Cellulose, Hemicellulose, Pectins and Gums," p. 61).

Macfayden and Blaxall (*loc. cit.*) thought that the fermentation was brought about by the combined action of symbiotic strains. Our present work seems to support this observation of Macfayden and Blaxall. We have started with horse-dung and been able to isolate two strains of bacteria which are weak cellulose fermenters separately, but which, when brought together, in the medium for cellulose fermentation, are capable of fermenting the cellulose under favourable circumstances, almost completely. Generally, however, a conversion of 50 to 60% of the cellulose is reached, the liquid products being acetic, formic and butyric acids and alcohol, and the gaseous product carbon dioxide, a large proportion of which is derived from the neutralisation of calcium carbonate by the produced acid. The activity of the two bacteria towards cellulose continues to diminish, till after six months, they showed very reduced function. To sugars and starches, however, they retained the usual initial activity. No explanation has yet been found for this deterioration, nor any specific means of reactivation. It should be noticed here that a large quantity of sulphuretted hydrogen, specially in the beginning of fermentation, is noticed, derived no doubt from the nutrient substances added to the medium. This symbiotic action is still more energetic in less purified enrichment cultures, a fact which would indicate that although some cellulose fermenters *per se* have been isolated, for technical degradation of cellulose, the symbiosis of more numerous types of bacteria is probably essential. If one disallows the purity of Viljoen-Fred-Peterson's bacterium as suggested by

Thaysen, the mechanism of the fermentation of cellulose in their case can also be considered to be due to symbiosis. In the case of the two types isolated by us, there is no inability on the part of either to ferment starch, sugars (hexoses and pentoses) or hemicelluloses. If we admit that in the degradation of cellulose, cellobiose and glucose are obligatory intermediates, then it is difficult to reconcile the behaviour of Madame Khouvine's organism or that of Hutchinson and Clayton's *Spirochaeta Cytophaga*, which are both characterised by their unique inability to ferment carbohydrates except cellulose.

So, far, the only large scale experiments on the fermentation of cellulose on record are those by Fowler and Joshi (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1920, **3**, 39), and the one described by Langwell and Lymn (*loc. cit.*). The observation of Fowler and Joshi that hemicelluloses were more suitable for fermentation than the more resistant celluloses, reduces the usefulness of their bacteria, no pure culture of which is on record. Tomoda (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind., Japan*, 1932, **35**, 534B) who appears to have isolated a species of *Clostridium thermocellum* as described by Viljoen, Fred and Peterson (*loc. cit.*) in determining mechanism of the decomposition of cellulose fibre by the action of microorganisms opines that this mechanism is quite different from that of the hydrolysis of cellulose or cellulose solution by acids. It would be important to reconcile this hypothesis with that of Pringsheim who regards cellobiose and glucose as the intermediates.

Method of isolation of the two types of cellulose fermenting bacteria.—2 G. of sun-dried horse-dung were kept in a watch glass for 4 hours at 55° to eliminate mesophilic organisms. The substance was then added to an enrichment medium of the following composition:

Dipotassium phosphate	... 0.1 g.	Potassium nitrate	... 0.2 g.
Magnesium sulphate	... 0.1	Strips of filter paper	... 2.0
Sodium chloride	... 0.1	Water	... 100 c. c.
Calcium carbonate	... 0.2	p_H adjusted to 7.4	

The whole was then heated on the water-bath for 10 minutes at about 75-80° and then incubated at 55° for about 5 days, when the filter paper was found to have commenced disintegrating. In 10 days' time the disintegration was practically complete, evolution of gas (methane, hydrogen and carbon dioxide) being noticed all the time. A portion of the disintegrated but still fibrous mass of the filter paper was taken out by a platinum loop and introduced into 5 c. c. of sterile

physiological solution (0.85% sodium chloride solution in distilled water) containing a few glass beads, in a test tube. The mass was thoroughly shaken, and 1 c. c. of it was added to a second lot (100 c. c.) of the enrichment medium and allowed to be incubated. After 4 days, a third enrichment was effected. From this actively fermenting enrichment, plating was done, the medium for plating being composed of trypsin-digested casein (100 c. c.), distilled water (850 c. c.), beef extract (1 g.), agar (30 g.), filter paper (finely subdivided) 10 g. and p_H 7.4. Starch-agar, glucose-agar and nutrient-agar were also tried for plating, but with indifferent results.

After 24 hours of incubation at 55° , which is found to be the optimum temperature two types of colonies appeared, which were almost similar in size, but one was *creamy white*, and the other *grey*. The two types were separately plated, with the result; however, that both the creamy white and the grey types reappeared in each of the plates, with this distinction that the number of grey colonies was disproportionately large in comparison with the creamy white ones. At first, the grey colonies being predominant, further purification of this type was effected by several platings (five times usually). Below is a micro-photograph of this type with a magnification of 1×1200 .

TYPE I.

Stained with carbinol fuchsin
for 30''—24 hours' growth.

TYPE II.

Stained with carbinol fuchsin
30''—24 hours' growth.

The action of this type on cellulose was very weak, a disappearance of 15-20% of the cellulose taken for fermentation being noticed at the

end of 7 days. This led to the suspicion that perhaps the type of organism having the creamy white colony might be responsible for the active fermentation of cellulose. Hence, this latter type was purified by repeated plating with the same medium and its action on cellulose investigated.

There was practically no action of the second type on cellulose. Both these isolated types, however, are capable of fermenting hemicelluloses, pentoses, sugars and starch, a fact which distinguishes them from Madame Khouvine's and Hutchinson and Clayton's organisms which can act only upon cellulose and on no other carbohydrate.

The qualitative nature of the gaseous products from the action of our bacteria on cellulose requires special mention. So far, all the organisms described give rise to methane, hydrogen and carbon dioxide in the impure stage, *i.e.*, in the enrichment stage, all those gases were found to be present. After purification by plating, neither hydrogen nor methane is evolved, the sole gaseous products being carbon dioxide and sulphuretted hydrogen. The latter no doubt is derived from medium.

* TABLE I.

Carbohydrate fermented.	Analyses of gases produced by the first type of bacterium.				
Arabinose	CO ₂	5.14%	4.5%	4.5%	5.0%
	CH ₄	...	...	...	...
	H ₂	...	...	...	...
Xylose	CO ₂	7.0	5.2	4.5	8.9
	CH ₄	...	...	...	...
	H ₂	...	...	...	...
Starch	CO ₂	3.65	4.5	3.4	7.9
	CH ₄	...	...	...	...
	H ₂	...	...	...	...
Molasses	CO ₂	32.2	39.0	52.0	...
	CH ₄	...	...	...	...
	H ₂	50.0	48.0	30.0	...

* The fermentation of molasses is characterised by the evolution of hydrogen, which is absent in other fermentations. In all these analyses, the residue was composed of nitrogen, oxygen and sulphuretted hydrogen in varying proportions. The second type of bacterium yielded similar results.

So far as the liquid products are concerned, there is no essential qualitative difference, acetic, formic and butyric acids in the main as also a certain percentage of ethyl alcohol being produced.

The following table shows the difference or otherwise of the analogous bacteria.

TABLE II.

Comparison of certain thermophilic cellulose fermenting bacteria.

	Langwell.	Fred. Peterson and Viljoen.	Sen and Das-Gupta. Type I.	Type II.
Size of rods.	4 × 0.4 μ	5 × 0.4 μ	4 × 0.75–1.0 μ	2 × 0.5 μ
Size of spore.	Not given	0.9 × 0.6 μ	2 × 1.0 μ	2 × 1.0–1.25 μ
Flagella.	Absent.	Peritrichous.	Absent.	Absent.
Gram-stain.	Negative.	Negative.	Negative.	Negative.
N. Broth with glucose.	Gas and acid.	Gas and acid.	Gas and acid. (sediment).	Gas and acid. (surface growth).
N. Agar stroke.	Shining, moist, butyrous.	Shining, moist, butyrous.	Dull, dry, butyrous. (slightly spreading).	Dry, creamy, butyrous (not spreading).
Potato slant.	Yellow, moist, potato browned.	Yellow, potato browned.	Grey, dry.	Creamy, potato slightly darkened.
N. Agar plate.	Small surface & sub-surface colonies.	Small sub-surface colonies. Profuse growth on starch agar.	Scanty growth surface colonies slightly spreading.	Scanty growth small surface colonies (smaller than Type I).
Milk.	Acid, curdled in 5 days.	Slightly acid in 3 days.	Slightly acid in 3 days. (no curdling).	Slightly acid in 3 days. (no curdling).
Carbohydrates fermented.	Cellulose, starch, hemicellulose, hexose & pentose, etc.	Cellulose, starch, hemicellulose, hexose & pentose, etc.	Hemicellulose, starch, hexose, pentose & cellulose slightly.	Hemicellulose, starch, hexose, pentose & cellulose slightly.

No liquefaction of gelatine or detection of sugar as intermediate product; nor indole formation noticed.

From a perusal of the above table, the separate identity of these two types of bacteria can be inferred, the most characteristic feature being the increased activity on symbiosis.

TABLE III.

The action of Type I on xylose, arabinose, starch, cotton, glucose, filter paper, rice-straw, and water hyacinth :

Substance fermented.	Substance taken as reducing sugar.	Fermenting period.	0.1 N acid formed.	Acid formed (expressed as acetic acid).	Alcohol formed.	Residue.
Straw digested	5 g.	3 days	265.6 c.c.	31.8%	—	62.0%
	5	5	484.0	58.08	5.3%	32.6
	5	7	726.0	87.12	6.27	0.6
Arabinose	5	3	200.8	24.1	—	61.0
	5	5	661.6	79.39	—	17.4
	5	7	664.0	79.68	3.0	16.4
Glucose	5	3	229.0	27.48	6.21	64.8
	5	5	650.0	78.0	6.98	13.86
Xylose	5	5	754.4	90.53	3.85	0.32
Starch	5	5	776.18	93.14	3.2	1.6
Water hyacinth digested	5	7	—	—	15.23	1.98
	5	7	—	—	11.90	—
	5	7	—	—	12.96	2.25
	5	7	—	—	11.99	—
Molasses	5.85	5	540.78	55.5	13.68	29.95
	5.85	5	518.34	53.26	10.96	35.9
	3.45	5	374.50	64.4	23.8	12.35
	4.18	5	468.48	67.23	19.47	14.05

Each set of experiment is the average of five experiments.

The action of Type II on xylose, glucose and hyacinth, etc., will be understood from the following table.

TABLE IV.

Substance fermented.	Substance taken as reducing sugar.	Fermenting period.	0.1 N Acid formed.	Acid formed (expressed as acetic acid).	Alcohol formed.	Residue.
Xylose	5 g.	5 days	624.0 c.c.	74.88%	6.50%	18.6%
Glucose	5	5	508.0	60.90	5.60	33.8
Hyacinth	5	7	—	—	13.25	11.37
	5	7	—	—	15.12	13.25

A comparative chart on the action of bacteria Type I and Type II individually and mixed together on cellulose is given below.

TABLE V.

Type I.			Type II.			Type I & II mixed together.		
Cellulose (filter paper)	Alcohol.	Acid (expressed as acetic).	Cellulose (filter paper)	Alcohol.	Acid. (acetic acid).	Cellulose (filter paper)	Alcohol.	Acid. (as acetic acid).
5g.	1.90%	13.26%	2g.	3.25%	13.56%	5g.	14.6%	68.87%
5	5.52	12.90	5	4.30	17.27	5	11.35	81.96
5	5.06	15.67	5	2.25	15.20	5	10.20	47.0

The effect of concentration of the sugar solution on the total fermentibility.—A 2% arabinose solution was fermented with the result that 26% sugar was left unacted, whilst the acid figure was 56.6 c.c. N/10 acid per g. of sugar. With a 1% arabinose solution the unacted sugar was 17% and the acid figure was 75.84 c.c. of N/10 acid.

The Influence of p_H Value of the Medium on Fermentibility.

$P_H = 6.6$	...	very slight growth.
$P_H = 7.0$	...	moderate growth.
$P_H = 7.4$	...	normal vigorous growth.

In the last instance, the p_H value decreased rapidly and soon reached a point (6.5–6.6) where activity was hampered by the slight acidity of the medium. 1% Calcium carbonate was, therefore, added to keep the p_H value steady between 7 and 7.4.

Influence of temperature.—At room temperature (28°–32°), there was no fermentation, but the organism lives. The optimum temperature was found to be 55°. The spores can resist steam-temperature (100°) for 10 minutes.

Analysis of the total fatty acids obtained from the fermentation of filter paper, arabinose and glucose, the proportions being in each practically the same. Butyric acid, 30%; formic acid, 25%; acetic acid, 45%. The estimation of these acids was done according to the following method: The total acid was at first treated with a baryta water and the whole was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. The residue was left in contact with absolute alcohol for 6 hours with occasional stirring. The soluble barium butyrate was separated by filtration, the alcohol evaporated on the water-bath and the butyric acid liberated by the addition of dilute sulphuric acid, distilled in steam and titrated. The residue left after extraction of barium butyrate, was steam-distilled in the presence of phosphoric acid. The distillate was treated with magnesium sulphate and evaporated to dryness. The dried mass was again extracted with absolute alcohol, when magnesium acetate went into solution. The solution was evaporated and the acetic acid liberated by dilute sulphuric acid as before and steam-distilled and estimated by titration. Similarly, formic acid remaining in the residue was estimated.

Estimation of alcohol.—10–12 G. of potassium dichromate were dissolved in water and 30–35 c.c. concentrated sulphuric acid were added to it. This mixture was used for oxidising the alcohol obtained in the distillate from the fermented liquor. This distillate amounted usually to 500 c.c., which was kept in contact with the oxidising mixture for 20 minutes and was then steam-distilled and the acetic acid was estimated.* It should be noted that perceptible quantities of butyric acid or even butyraldehyde were present in this distillate,

* The distillation was continued till a few drops of the distillate showed an exceedingly weak test for acid with blue litmus paper. The total distillate was titrated against $N/5$ alkali, and the result expressed in term of ethyl alcohol, assuming the whole of the acid to be acetic acid.

proving the presence of butyl alcohol in the fermentation process. This method, which is a shortened form of Docks and Lamb's process, gave good results. Experiments with absolute alcohol agreed up to 97% usually.

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